

Microwave assisted synthesis of 2,3-disubstituted-4-thiazolidinones and their pharmacological screening

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Six title compounds have been synthesized by condensation of substituted (4-methyl-2-quinolinyl)oxyacetic acid hydrazide (1) with aryl aldehydes followed by reaction with thioglycolic acid in dioxane under microwave irradiation. All the compounds are screened for their central nervous system and cardiovascular system activities.

Quinoline derivatives and 4-thiazolidinones are known for exhibiting diverse pharmacological activities¹. The application of microwave irradiation (MWI) for rapid organic synthesis has found widespread use due to substantial reduction in reaction time^{2,3}. Keeping this in view, we undertook the synthesis of the title compounds by condensation of substituted (4-methyl-2-quinolinyl)oxyacetic acid hydrazide with aryl aldehydes followed by reaction with thioglycolic acid in dioxane under MWI as well as conventional method.

The toxicity and gross central nervous system (CNS) activity were tested in mice. Compounds 3a-f were found to be moderately toxic and CNS stimulants, they increased the SMA (spontaneous motor activity) and reactivates to sound and though induced reactivity at all the tested doses. Cardiovascular system (CVS) activity of compounds 3a-f were tested at doses of 1.0, 2.5, 5.0, 10.0 mg/kg (i.v.) in cat. Compound 3e was found to be effective as compared to the other compounds.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined on a Thomas-Hoover apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R-21 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (pyridine-d₅) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel-G coated Al plates (Merck). Elemental analysis were performed on a Heraceus analyser.

Substituted 2-(4-methyl-2-quinolinyl)oxyacetylhydrazones (2a-f): A solution of the hydrazide³ (1; 0.01 mol) and arylaldehyde (0.01 mol) in methanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 2-3 h. Excess of solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol.

3-(4-Methyl-2'-quinolinyl)oxyacetamido-2-(substituted-phenyl)-4-thiazolidinones (3a-f): *Method A (Classical method)*: To a solution of the substituted hydrazone (2a-f;

3a	R=H	3d	R=CH ₃
3b	R=Cl	3e	R=OH
3c	R=NO ₂	3f	R=OCH ₃

Table 1. Physical and spectral data of compounds 3a-f*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %		ν _{max}	δ
		Method A	Method B		
3a	257–259	72	85	3250 (NH), 2825 (CH ₂), 1730, 1675 (cyclic and acyclic C=O), 1285, 1075 (C–O–C)	2.20 (3H, s, 4'-CH ₃), 3.10 (1H, s, NCH), 3.75 (2H, s, SCH ₂), 4.67 (2H, s, CH ₂ CO), 6.60 (1H, s, H-3'), 7.10–7.45 (9H, m, ArH), 9.40 (1H, br, CONH)
b	205–207	76	89	3240 (NH), 2820 (CH ₂), 1720, 1660 (cyclic and acyclic C=O), 795 (C–Cl)	2.10 (3H, s, 4'-CH ₃), 3.00 (1H, s, NCH), 3.80 (2H, s, SCH ₂), 4.68 (2H, s, CH ₂ CO), 6.42 (1H, s, H-3'), 7.20–7.50 (8H, m, ArH), 9.57 (1H, br, CONH)
c	245–246	72	83	3250 (NH), 2825 (CH ₂), 1720, 1680 (cyclic and acyclic C=O), 1545–1355 NO ₂ , 1285, 1075 (C–O–C)	2.20 (3H, s, 4'-CH ₃), 3.10 (1H, s, NCH), 3.75 (2H, s, SCH ₂), 4.58 (2H, s, CH ₂ CO), 6.45 (1H, s, H-3'), 7.20–7.50 (8H, m, ArH), 9.52 (1H, br, CONH)
d	258	79	92	3235 (NH), 2820 (CH ₂), 1728, 1670 (cyclic and acyclic C=O), 1280, 1080 (C–O–C)	2.25 (6H, s, 2 × CH ₃), 3.20 (1H, s, NCH), 3.80 (2H, s, SCH ₂), 4.65 (2H, s, CH ₂ CO), 6.42 (1H, s, H-3'), 7.25–7.70 (8H, m, ArH), 9.55 (1H, br, CONH)
e	258–259	73	82	3410 (OH), 3280 (NH), 2830 (CH ₂), 1725, 1660 (cyclic and acyclic C=O), 1280, 1060 (C–O–C)	2.15 (3H, s, 4'-CH ₃), 3.20 (1H, s, NCH), 3.80 (2H, s, SCH ₂), 4.68 (2H, s, CH ₂ CO), 6.40 (1H, s, H-3'), 7.20–7.65 (8H, m, ArH), 9.50 (1H, br, CONH), 11.60 (1H, br, OH)
f	232	78	92	3210 (NH), 2825 (CH ₂), 1730, 1680 (cyclic and acyclic C=O), 1265, 1076 (C–O–C)	2.20 (3H, s, 4'-CH ₃), 3.10 (1H, s, NCH), 3.60 (2H, s, SCH ₂), 3.90 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 4.58 (2H, s, CH ₂ CO), 6.48 (1H, s, H-3'), 7.20–7.65 (8H, m, ArH), 9.57 (1H, br, CONH)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

0.01 mol) in dioxane (50 ml), thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 8–10 h. Excess of solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the resulting residue was poured in ice-cold water. The solid obtained was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from ethanol.

Method B (Microwave method) : The mixture (as in Method A) was subjected to microwave irradiation at 2450 MHz for 8–10 min. It was then cooled and worked up as described in Method A.

All compounds were tested for their action on CNS and lethality on albino mice of either sex. For toxicity tests, the compounds were injected i.p. in 5% aqueous gum acacia suspension to each group (n = 5) of mice (20–25 g) at different doses (464 and 1000 mg/kg). After 24 h, mortality of animals was noted and the LD₅₀ was evaluated⁴. The gross CNS activities were observed at aforesaid doses along with dose 1/5th of LD₅₀. Behavioural changes in spontaneous motor activity (SMA) and reactivities to sound and touch were observed after 1 h of injection.

Cardiovascular system (CVS) activity was evaluated on adult cats (3–4 kg) of either sex. Sodium pentobarbital 40 mg/kg (i.p.) was used for anaesthetizing the cats. The right common carotid artery was cannulated and the blood pressure recorded. All the test drugs and reference agents (acetylchlorine, adrenaline, histamine) were administered through an indwelling polythene cannula in the right femoral vein.

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